

APPROACH TO LEGAL RESEARCH

(An Introduction to the Study of Analysis of Western Law and Islamic Law)

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Abstract

This study discusses the methodological approach in legal research that is studied in the perspective of western law and Islamic law. In examining this title, the writer uses descriptive analysis method, so that it is expected to be able to produce a comprehensive understanding. The types of approaches in legal research include: a historical approach, a case approach, an analytical approach, a philosophical approach, a comparative approach and a statutory approach. Output from legal research are provisions in the form of instructions, recommendations or suggestions. As an applied science, the resulting instructions must be applicable in the middle of social life (applicable), not something that is imaginary and wishful thinking. From this research it is hoped that researchers will be able to use these approaches according to the type of data required in a series of research activities, by looking at the reality of people's lives as an element of the substance of legal research. Researchers are also expected to be able to choose an approach that suits the object of research, while solving a legal issue can be done through legal research with certain approaches as a basis for formulating appropriate arguments.

Keywords: Approaches in Legal Research, Western Law, Islamic Law

1. Introduction

In a study, legal research is no exception, in principle, there is a reason to hunt down

scientific truths that are believed to exist in every phenomenon and event. The research activity has the aim of forming, developing, or at least updating Science. With such research objectives, the chain of knowledge will not be broken because it is continually updated according to the context of the needs of a society with character changeable, that is, it can change to the rhythm of changing places and times.

Meanwhile, science itself has three important elements which each have a binding relationship, namely substance, information and methodology.¹ On this basis, the actual research framework follows the structure of the science so that it can form scientific truth that can be accounted for academically.

Substance as the first element of knowledge in research work is often referred to as a research problem. The determination of this research problem begins with the occurrence of academic problems that underlie why a study is feasible. From the academic anxiety that is usually expressed in the background of this problem then flows and converges into the focus of research in which research problems are formulated. Then the formulation of this problem is equipped with the direction and objectives of the research so that it does not escape from the point of orbit.

We can interpret information as the second element of science as a frame of mind in analyzing research problems. That is, frame-work The researcher automatically transforms into information in analyzing the problems that have been formulated in the previous research focus. Therefore, in research work, apart from showing the theoretical basics as well as the results of previous research so that this kind of information will become guideline for researchers in analyzing research data.

Whereas methodology as the third element of science is nothing but a series of research work. Some say that methodology is the science of research methods. Others have interpreted it more practically that a methodology is a collection of methods used, starting from the preliminary study stage, determining data sources, collecting data, organizing data and analyzing data. The research method was chosen according to the characteristics of the substance and information elements.

Therefore, it is not surprising that in a large body of research we find many varieties and types. This type of research ranges from a very abstract philosophical character to the types of research methods that are very applicable and ready to be used as a practical guide. As for legal research, the required data is in the form of social symptoms that occur in society.

¹ Abu Yazid, *Aspek-Aspek Penelitian Hukum, Hukum Barat-Hukum Islam*, Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar, 2009, p.1

Therefore, legal research can be classified into social science research. In fact, the real empiricism of law has developed in such a way until now. Therefore, without a doubt people include it as a relative of social science so that the use of legal research methods is also not much different from that used in the social sciences. The types of data collected in legal research are also no different from social science research, namely in the form of facts and realities with natural backgrounds and occur phenomenologically.

Output from legal research are provisions in the form of instructions, recommendations or suggestions. As an applied science, the instructions that must be generated from legal research must be applicable in social life. In other words, the hints and suggestions that constitute the stipulation are not in the form of delusions and wishful thinking high in the clouds. On the contrary, it must be applicable according to the character of empirical law science.

According to Abu Yazid,² the output in the form of this provision in Islamic law is known as product fiqh. Meanwhile, the analytical tool in the form of a rational thinking frame is called process fiqh. Process fiqh in this context is synonymous with scientific reasoning which has the excuse of how the text of revelation can be grounded so that it can take the form of legal rules which then become the foothold of mankind in its social institutions. Islamic law, thus, even though it involves human reasoning in the process of its formation, it still has references to revelation texts both in detail and in micro (*juz'i / tafshili*) as well as abstractly and macro (*kulli / ijmal*).

As for the reality of life as a substance, in legal research, it has a character that changes from time to time. Character changeable This then necessitates variation in the approach to research subjects. In Islamic legal research, this variation of approach is also motivated by a fairly long historical stretch between the period of revelation and our current real conditions. Realities like this inevitably require a researcher to choose an approach that suits the research object. Because solving a legal issue through legal research requires certain approaches as a basis for formulating appropriate arguments.

2. Formulation of the problem

Ber based on the description above, the author will discuss several legal research approaches that can be used according to the type of data required in a series of research activities. So in this paper the authors formulate a problem related to what is meant by the historical approach, the case approach, the analytical approach, the philosophical approach, the comparative approach and the statutory approach. invitation (statute approach)?

² *Ibid*, p. 5

3. Discussion

3.1 Historical Approach

This approach is carried out in the framework of understanding the philosophy of the rule of law from time to time, as well as understanding changes and developments in the philosophy underlying these legal rules. This approach is carried out by examining the background and regulatory developments regarding the legal issues at hand.

In Western legal research, a historical approach is carried out within the framework of tracking the history of legal institutions from time to time. This approach is very helpful for researchers to understand the philosophy of the rule of law that has developed in history. In addition, through this approach, researchers can also understand changes and developments in the philosophy that underlie these legal rules.³

Each statutory regulation has a different historical background. By knowing the historical background, then making these statutory rules, legal practitioners will have the same interpretation of legal issues that have been regulated in the legislation in question. According to a historical perspective, there are two kinds of interpretations of laws and regulations, namely:

- a) Interpretation according to legal history,
- b) Interpretation according to the history of the stipulation of laws and regulations.⁴

Normative legal research that uses a historical approach allows a researcher to understand the law more deeply about a system or institution, or a certain legal arrangement so as to minimize errors, both in understanding and applying a particular institution or legal provisions.⁵

The law of the present and the law of the past is a unit that is closely related, continuous and unbroken so that it is said that we can understand the law of the present by studying history. The current legal system contains elements from the past legal system and forms the branches of the legal system in the future.⁶

In Islamic legal research, a historical approach is also commonly used by jurists. Even in order to explore the context that underlies the process of revelation, theory emerged *asbab al-nuzul* (because of the revelation of the verses of the Koran), *asbab al-wurud* (because of the

³ Peter Mahmud Marzuki, *Penelitian Hukum*, Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Group, 2007, p. 126.

⁴ Johnny Ibrahim, *Teori & Metodologi Penelitian Hukum Normatif*, Malang: Bayumedia Publishing, 2006, p. 318

⁵ Satjipto Raharjo, *Ilmu Hukum*, Bandung: Alumni, 1986, p. 332.

⁶ Kusumadi Pudjosewojo, *Pedoman Pelajaran Tata Hukum Indonesia*, Jakarta: New Script, 1976, p. 11.

birth of al-Hadith), principles *al-tadarruj fi al-tasyri* ' (the stages of coming of shari'ah), *nasikh mansukh* (the text of one paragraph can replace the legal position of another paragraph), *al-ta'arudl wa al-tarjih*(selection mechanism in case of text polarization) and the like. Theories like this make us aware of the importance of exposing the internal link between the revealed text and the context of the reality of human life.

As a form of explanation of the theory *asbab al-nuzul* and *asbab al-wurud* then appeared maxims which reads: "al-'ibrah bi khususi al-sabab la bi 'Umumi al-lafzh" (What holds the rule of law is the specificity of the birth of the text, not the generality of the text editor).

This rule places the historical context above the generality and universality of text editors who have a legal dimension. In this context the historical approach to legal research has relevance. However, this does not mean that this theory is avoided from criticism from jurisprudence experts in the history of Islamic legal thought. Because, with this rule, the existence of a practical text cannot reproduce meanings for other legal cases. Therefore, the majority of Islamic jurists criticize this rule and then they bring up another rule as an antithesis, namely: "al-'ibrah bi 'Umumi al-lafzh la bi khususi al-sabab" (What holds the rule of law is the general editorial of the text. , not specificity because of the decline in the text).

This second rule clearly places the universality of the text in a very central position, surpassing the context of social reality with its various changes. On the other hand, the historical context of human experience by this rule is placed in a very inferior particular position. Reality like this in turn can knock down the concept building *asbab al-nuzul* and others which he pain stakingly built into the epistemology of his own knowledge. This rule actually cannot be practiced in general in all texts. This is because not all texts have a general editorial relationship pattern on the one hand and specifically the reasons for the decline on the other. On the other hand, there are not a few teaching texts that have the same general pattern, both editorial and historical, or vice versa, both the editorial staff of the text and the reasons for its derivation are equally specific. In this connection the distortion of the use of such knowledge *asbab al-nuzul* can be avoided. Because of that, the historical approach in Islamic legal research still has a place and is in fact often used by legal experts in its history.

3.2 Case Approach

This approach is carried out by analyzing cases related to the legal issues at hand. The cases that are reviewed are cases that have received a final court decision. The main thing that is studied in each decision is the judge's consideration to arrive at a decision so that it can be used as an argument in solving the legal issue at hand.

In contrast to social research, the case approach (*case approach*) in normative research aims to study the application of legal norms or rules that are carried out in legal practice. Especially regarding cases that have been decided as can be seen in the jurisprudence of cases that are the focus of research. It is clear that the cases that have occurred have an empirical meaning, but in a normative study, these cases are studied to obtain an overview of the impact of the dimensions of norming in a rule of law in legal practice, and to use the results of the analysis for input (*input*) in legal explanation.⁷

In using the case approach, what researchers need to understand are the legal reasons used in the previous decision-making process. The legal reasons for this can be found by paying attention to material facts in the form of person, place, time, and everything that accompanies them. Material facts need attention because proper legal rules are sought and attempted to be applied to these facts. This legal reason shows that law science is a prescriptive, not descriptive science. Meanwhile, the verdict (*dictum*) is something that is descriptive in nature. Therefore, the case approach does not refer to the *dictum* of court decisions, but rather refers to legal reasons and considerations.⁸

In Islamic law, the case approach is carried out by equating new legal cases with old legal cases where there are provisions *reasoning* in the holy text. The effort to equalize this is done because there are similarities *reasoning* between one case and another. This approach to cases in Islamic law is called analogy or *qiyas*.

If it is relaxed again, the real case approach is not limited to mechanisms *qiyas*. On the contrary, with reference to the theory *maqashid al-syari'ah* a case approach can be done by looking for a common thread between every legal incident that occurs with the general purpose of enforcing Islamic law, namely *lijalb al-rnashalih wa dar'i al-mafasid* (to bring benefit and avoid damage). With such a pattern, every legal case that arises in the community can be traced to its legal provisions by referring to the arguments *kulli* (macro and abstract) in Islamic teachings, not limited to argument *juz'i* (micro and detail) as in practice *qiyas*.

3.3 Analytical Approach

The main purpose of analysis of legal materials is to know the meaning contained by the terms used in statutory regulations conceptually, as well as to know their application in practice and legal decisions. This was done through two checks. First, the researcher tries to get new meanings contained in the law rules concerned. Second, testing these legal terms in

⁷Johnny Ibrahim, *Teori & Metodologi Petielitian Hukum Normatif*, without year, p. 321.

⁸Peter Mahmud Marzuki, *Legal Research*, without year, p. 119.

practice through analysis of legal decisions.⁹

Basically, this approach is to analyze the meaning of law, legal principles, legal principles, legal systems, and various juridical concepts. For example, the juridical concept of legal subjects, legal objects, property rights, marriage, agreements, engagements, work relations, buying and selling, achievements, defaults, illegal acts, offenses, and so on.¹⁰

This analytical approach is considered very important because the content of law is a form of organism that lives and moves dynamically in order to respond to the various developments in very complex legal issues today. Nasr Hamid Abu Zaid, an Islamic thinker from Egypt, quoted Sayyidina Ali ra, once emphasized that the Koran is a silent text and only humans are able to make it live and speak.¹¹ Therefore, the analytical approach to the text has its own relevance to give birth to dynamic legal dictums.

On another occasion Nasr Hamid indicated that the Islamic civilization that was developing today was a text civilization. The position of the text is so central that it is able to develop the foundations of civilization and science. For Nasr Hamid, it is not the independence of the text that can frame the birth of culture and science. On the other hand, a cultural framework and a reflection of science can only emerge through the long struggle of mankind with its social reality, in addition to human debates regarding the meaning of the text itself.¹²

In fact, text is born not in an empty space. Therefore, it always needs to be analyzed for its meaning and legal content. Text always appears as the social context continues to evolve. Of course, the text in this case has a broad meaning regarding texts that are integrated with the context of the historical experience of mankind. The integration of this text and context needs to be analyzed because in fact God's law was not born except for the context of the welfare and benefit of mankind throughout its history.

3.4 Philosophical Approach

The task of philosophy, as Socrates said, is not to answer the questions asked, but to question the answers given. Therefore, explanations in philosophy include ontological teachings (teachings about nature), axiology (teachings about values), epistemological teachings (teachings about knowledge), and theological teachings (teachings about goals) to

⁹Johnny Ibrahim, *Op.Cit*, p. 310.

¹⁰*Ibid*, p. 311.

¹¹Nasr Hamid Abu Zaid, *Naqd al-Khitab al-Dini*, in the Indonesian edition, Criticism of Religious Discourse, Yogyakarta: LKiS, 2003, p. 91.

¹²Nasr Hamid Abu Zaid, *Mafhum al-Nash: Dirasah fi Ulum al-Qur'an*, Egypt: Al-Hai'ah Al-Mishriyyah Al-Ammah Li Al-Kitab, 1993, p. 11.

clarify in depth as far as the attainment of human knowledge allows. The study of philosophy begins with the attitude of a scientist who is humble, has the courage to self-correct, is straightforward in providing a justification for the answer to the question whether the current mastered science includes all existing knowledge, at which limit does science begin and at which limit it stops. and what are the advantages and disadvantages of that knowledge.¹³

Based on the characteristics of this philosophy, assisted by several correct approaches, what should be done *called fundamental research*, that is, a study to gain a deeper understanding of the social implications and effects of the application of laws and regulations on society or groups of people that involve research on history, philosophy, linguistics, economics, and the social and political implications of the enforcement of a rule of law.¹⁴

In the Islamic perspective, the philosophical approach is highly appreciated so that one of the popular topics of discussion in legal studies is *hikmah al-tasyri 'wa falsafatuhu* (wisdom and philosophy of the formation of Islamic law).¹⁵ In addition, there are a number of rules that lead to the philosophical aspects of the formation of Islamic law. This is like the rule of Islamic law as follows:

a) "*La dharara wa la dhirara* " (It is forbidden to bring up kemudaratan and return something with kemudaratan).

This rule has its origins in the hadith text which was later adopted into a general rule (al-qa'idah al-kubra) in Islamic law. When philosophically Islamic law is always oriented towards the principles of benefit and benefit, then these rules are made.

b) "*al-masyaqqah tajlibu al-taisir*" (narrowness can bring relief)

This principle is also built on the philosophy of the formation of Islamic law. When the dictums of Islamic law always pay attention and provide a way out when humans are in a condition of narrowness and difficulty, this law rule is made. Philosophically, this principle also refers to a number of revelatory texts that are oriented towards looseness and comfort in an effort to enforce legal rules.¹⁶

c) "*al-'adah muhak Court*" (Customs can be used as legal standards)

What has been institutionalized and has become a custom can actually be considered a

¹³Johnny Ibrahim, *Theory 6. Metodologi Penelitian Hukum Normatif*, p. 320.

¹⁴*Ibid.*

¹⁵This theme is also the title of a quite popular book written by al-Ustadz al-Shaykh Ali Ahmad al-Jurjawi, printed by Dar al-Fikr, tp, tt.

¹⁶A number of revelation texts that support the formation of this rule are: QS al-Baqarah: 172,185, 286; QS al-Nisa ': 28; QS al-Ma'idah: 6; QS al-Hajj: 78; The Prophet's hadith which reads: *بُعِثْتُ بِالْخَيْفَةِ السَّمْحَةَ* (*I was sent with great ease*.HR. Imam Ahmad); as well as the Prophet's hadith that was uttered when he sent his friends Abu Dzarrah and Mu'adz bin Jabal to Yemen: *يسرا ولا تعسرا وبشرا ولا تنفرا* (*Make it easy by you and don't make it difficult. tell you the good news and don't make them run*.HR Imam al-Bukhari). In another hadith it is related that every Rasulullah SAW. offered two law cases he did not choose except for a lighter one as long as the case was not filled with sin.

value (*value*) which has a positive dimension is preserved. Therefore, philosophically Islamic law must be based on customary values which are conventionally established by a community. So much is the appreciation of Islamic law for customs that it is formally established as a source of law.

3.5 Comparative Approach

This approach is carried out by comparing legal regulations or court decisions in one country with legal regulations in other countries (can be 1 country or more), but it must be about the same thing. Comparisons are made to obtain similarities and differences between the legal regulations / court decisions.

The comparative approach in law is considered important because as a normative science it does not allow an experiment to be carried out as is usually done in empirical science. The comparative approach is one of the ways used in normative research to compare a legal institution from one legal system to another legal institution (which is more or less the same as the legal system). From this comparison, elements of the similarities and differences between the two legal systems can be found. The similarities will show the essence of the legal institutions investigated, while the differences caused by differences in climate, atmosphere, and history of each nation are associated with different legal systems. Furthermore, by making legal comparisons it can be concluded that:

- a. The same universal needs give rise to the same ways of organizing.
- b. Special needs based on differences in atmosphere and history give rise to different ways.¹⁷

The logical consequence of comparative legal studies will lead a researcher to the history of law and it cannot be avoided. Comparative law has an empirical dimension that can be used as an auxiliary science for the purposes of analysis and explanation of law. The comparative approach is empirical and interdisciplinary in nature so that it can be used in normative research to identify social conditions and determine forms of normalization. Thus, normative research can and should take advantage of the results of empirical research, but empirical science has the status of an auxiliary science so that it does not change the essence of law science as a normative science. In general, the comparative approach is carried out using micro comparisons, namely comparing the contents of specific legal rules of other countries with the legal rules under study, or it could be in order to fill in the blanks in positive law. Such research is only carried out on elements that can be compared with the legal material which is the focus of the research.¹⁸

¹⁷Johnny Ibrahim, *Teori & Metodologi Penelitian Hukum Normatif*, Op.Cit, p. 313.

¹⁸*Ibid*, p. 314-315

In Islamic law, the comparative approach is carried out dialectically to test the validation of the arguments presented by each of the different legal provisions. As we all know that Islamic legal documents are full of differences of opinion between one legal expert and another. This is due to their unconventional vision in absorbing the provisions of the revelation text which are global and multiple interpretations. In addition, the benefit variable that must be considered in every legal event in society also conditions the complexity of the differentiation of opinions that is difficult to contain.

In the event that there are several legal opinions regarding an event that occurred, the mechanism *tarjih* or selecting the opinion that deserves to be elected is unavoidable. Comparing one opinion with another legal opinion is not easy. Therefore, in Islamic legal thought, *tarjih* work falls into the category of *ijtihad* in certain strata.¹⁹

In the order of *ijtihad*, it is stated that the highest order is *ijtihad mutlaq* (independent), namely *ijtihad* using methodology *istinbath* which he built himself in an effort to bring forth operational laws. Like the *ijtihad* carried out by Imam Abu Hanifah, Imam al-Syafi'i, Imam Malik, Imam Ahmad bin Hanbal, Imam al-Auza'i and others. The second place is *ijtihad madzhab*, which is to explore the content of law using the methodology developed by the Imam's predecessor. Like the *ijtihad* carried out by Imam al-Muzanni who still uses the Imam al-Shafi'i methodology. Or *ijtihad* by Imam Abu Yusuf using Imam Abu Hanifah's methodology. Meanwhile, in third place is *ijtihad fatwa*, namely *ijtihad* by comparing one opinion with another and selecting them based on the level of validation of the arguments and arguments presented. Like the *ijtihad* that is often carried out by Imam al-Nawai and al-Rafi'i in the shafi'iyah school of thought.²⁰

Apart from referring to the validation of the arguments of the revelation text in an explicit manner, comparing legal opinions with *tarjih* mechanisms must also consider the arguments *kulli* implicitly in the form of general principles. In this context, several measuring tools that must be considered are the extent to which legal opinions reflect more grace, provide easy access, are more in line with the social context, and are more in realizing the objectives of Islamic law, namely to spread benefit and reduce damage.

3.6 Statute Approach

This approach is carried out by examining all laws and regulations related to the problem (legal issue) being faced. This statutory approach, for example, is carried out by

¹⁹Abu Yazid, *Op.Cit.*, P. 84

²⁰*Ibid*, p. 85.

studying the consistency / suitability between the Basic Law and the Law, or between one Law and another, etc.

Certainly, normative research must use a statutory approach, because what will be examined are various legal rules that become the focus as well as the central theme of a study. For this reason, researchers must see the law as a closed system which has the following characteristics.

- a) *Comprehensive* meaning that the legal norms contained in it are logically related to one another.
- b) *All-inclusive* that the set of legal norms is sufficient to accommodate existing legal problems, so that there will be no legal shortages.
- c) *Systematic* that in addition to being intertwined with one another, the said legal norms are also arranged hierarchically.²¹

From this explanation, it can be seen that legal analysis is produced by a normative legal research that uses a statute approach. This analysis will be more accurate if it is assisted by one or more other suitable approaches in order to enrich appropriate legal considerations to deal with the legal problems at hand. The comparative approach with positive legal materials from several countries will make the resulting legal analysis more comprehensive and accurate. In addition, it shows that the results of normative legal research that answer legal problems in a concrete and factual manner actually contribute to and have an economic impact on improving people's welfare.²²

The statutory approach is considered important in legal research because in fact the legal provisions are produced for nothing but application. By referring to a certain statutory system, the resulting legal material will be more in line with the sense of justice in society. Certain statutory systems are nothing but a legal product through in-depth studies. Therefore, this statutory approach will greatly assist legal research work to find new prescriptions in accordance with the level of development of society.

In Islamic law, research has the aim of finding prescriptions (*istinbath*) and simultaneously apply it in the community (*tathbiq*). The purpose of implementing the law in society really requires legislation (*taqnin*) so that the legal product found is not just wishful thinking on the cloud. With this objective, a statutory approach is absolutely necessary in legal research work.

With a statutory approach, it is hoped that legal products are not only built for empty

²¹Johnny Ibrahim, *Teori & Metodologi Penelitian Hukum Normatif*, Op.Cit, p. 302-303.

²²Ibid, p. 305-306.

space. On the contrary, he participated in solving problems as a product of legislation in a law in a particular country. By transforming into positive law, the goal of tathbiq can be maximally realized. However, the objectives of legislation are not the only ones idealized in Islamic law. In general, Islamic law is also expected to be applied through a high legal awareness.

In the concept of implementing this law, the Caliph Uthman bin 'Affan once said: "*yaza'u Allaha bi al-sulthan ma la yaza'u bi al-qur'an*" (Allah uses government power over legal cases that cannot be handled. *live* by the Koran).²³

From this expression, the approach can be taken right in the effort implementing legal provisions are twofold kinds, namely:

- 1) *wazi 'qur'ani*, namely the power of the Koran or religion in providing legal guidance for social life;
- 2) *wazi 'sulthani*, namely the power of government by making legislation in the form of positive law to guard the implementation of the law.

4. Conclusion

From the description above, the authors can draw the conclusion that *the output* from legal research are provisions in the form of instructions, recommendations or suggestions. As an applied science, the resulting instructions must be applicable in social life (applicable), not something imaginary and wishful thinking. A researcher is required to be able to use these approaches according to the type of data required in a series of research activities, by looking at the reality of community life as an element of the substance of legal research. Researchers are also required to be able to choose an approach that is in accordance with the object of research, while solving a legal issue can be done through legal research with certain approaches as a basis for formulating appropriate arguments. As for scientific truth, it is not the same as absolute truth which only belongs to God. Scientific truth refers to a process rather than a product. That is, a truth can be called scientific if the search process is carried out in a programmed, directed and systemized manner. As for the product, scientific truth actually has a character *relative* or relative, so that it needs to be developed further with different research areas. Therefore, at the level of legal research, the theoretical findings generated qualitatively need to be followed up with quantitative research so that the legal theory can be tested again for its validity.

²³Jamaluddin 'Athiyah, *Nahwa Taf'il Maqashid al-Syari'ah*, Damascus: Dar Al-Fikr, 2001, p. 50.

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